

Local Government in Croatia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Dario Runtic

NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe
with the support of the Association of Cities in the Republic of Croatia

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Croatia: An Introduction

Dario Runtic, *NALAS Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

The Croatian governance system is rather centralized with limited scope of competencies and decision-making decentralized to local level. In recent years, the national legislative process became more open to general public input through an e-participation platform, open data portals launched and public participation in decision-making became formally obligatory.

The Constitution guarantees freedom of expression and access to the information, right to referenda, right to local governance and right to directly participate in decision-making at the local level for Croatian and EU citizens.

The right of access to the information is further prescribed in the national Law on Access to the Information which applies to all levels of government. The law defines the procedure of the access and reuse of the information, obligation of proactive publishing of the information, mandatory consultations with the public and open data. Public authorities are required by the law to disclose requested information to the citizens proactively by publishing key legislation, general acts, reports, etc. via their web site in electronic and machine readable formats. They are also required to respond within 15 days to any citizen requests for information using the most viable method of information delivery and citizens can use the obtained information freely.

All public authorities are required to consult the public during the legislative process or preparing general acts, strategic or planning acts which affect rights and interests of citizens and legal persons. The authorities are obligated to publish draft acts on the national e-consultation platform or their web pages for a period of 30 days with a request for public input. Failure to do so may result in courts rendering such acts null and void.

The right to referenda is defined in a national Law on Referenda and Other Means of Personal Participation in State and Local Affairs. Parliament can, at its own decision or at the request of 10 per cent of the voters, start national referenda on changes and amendments to the Constitution and legislation, including new legislation. The President, at the request of the government or jointly with the Prime Minister, can start referenda on changes of the Constitution or other issue of importance for independence and preserving of the Republic. The national referenda must be held in case of the Republic joining the unions with other states. Decision at the referenda is passed by the majority vote under condition majority of voters voted at the referenda.

Local referenda can be started on local legislative issues, termination of a mayor's mandate or other issues within the scope of local government. Local referenda can be initiated by 1/3 of the members of the representative body, the majority of town quarters/neighborhood

councils, the mayor or 20 per cent of voters. In all cases, except in the case of 20 per cent of voters, the representative body must discuss the proposal and may call a referendum by absolute majority vote within 30 days. In case 20 per cent of voters initiated the referendum, within 60 days the Ministry of Administration will verify whether the initiative complies with regulation and the local representative body will call a referendum within 30 days.

Advisory referenda can be called by the government to obtain opinion of the residents of one or several local or regional government units about the territorial-administrative structure of that area. Local governments can call an advisory referendum for issues within its competencies. Decision is passed by the majority vote unconditionally.

Citizens' meetings can be organized by the neighborhood council to collect input on issues of local (neighborhood) relevance, discussion on needs and interest of the citizens or for resolving local issues. The process and voting process is defined by local statutes and bylaws. Voting is public unless participants decide differently. The decision of a citizens meeting is obligatory for neighborhood council or town quarter, but it is not obligatory for the representative body of the local government. Hence, the latter could overturn decisions adopted by the citizens meeting.

In general, the legislative framework is generally permissive for public participation in decision-making in Croatia at all government levels. A permissive legislative framework does not necessarily translate into an enabling or encouraging framework. Administrative fragmentation, three layers of government and overlapping competencies of different levels of government do not provide for broad coverage, individual responsibility, innovation and significant impact in governance which may be an additional reason why a limited number of citizens engage in decision-making process. Other reasons may be of historical nature – a significant number of the voters lived in a central government top-bottom authoritative or semi-authoritative era with limited incentives for participation in the decision-making process, which gradually changed over the last quarter of the century. Government entities, likewise, were used to operate without soliciting input of the public or plainly limiting public availability of drafts. The change of both governance procedures and public interest is supported by recent report findings. The Freedom of Information Commissioner 2018 Report notes that a number of inputs submitted via the national e-consultation platform nearly doubled compared to 2017 and the number of inputs that were accepted and shaped the new legislation or acts increased from 25.2 per cent in 2017 to 33 per cent in 2018. Although the exact number of individual participants is not disclosed, a total number of 11,739 inputs suggest the number of participants is still rather low. The increase in number of inputs is related to an increased acceptance and use of e-consultation platform by the state bodies. There were approx. 640 laws and regulations published at national e-consultation platform in 2017 and 980 laws and regulations in 2018. The increase of accepted inputs (inputs which were incorporated in draft legislation) is probably related to more proficient input offered by professional individuals or organizations who followed suit and joined the platform.

The non-encouraging legislative framework, slow and formal instruments of participation yielding limited results are nowadays being challenged by social media, digital platforms, on-line petitioning, virtual interest groups, instant think-thanks, etc.

Local governments are required by law to carry out public consultations in relation to local regulation and general acts using their web pages or national electronic system. At this point, access to a national electronic system is not available although it is being discussed between the state and national local government associations. Therefore, urban and rural local governments are using their web pages to enable public consultations, often by publishing an act and an offline form that can be submitted to the local government. There does not appear to be much difference in urban and rural practice. City of Rijeka seems to be attracting more substantial input and broader participation in its legislative and planning activities. The City of Rijeka launched an e-consultation platform in 2011, two years before consultations became a legal requirement and they seem to be the only one (or one of the few) to offer on-line submission of citizens' inputs. Early start coupled with on-line form suggests long-term effort and frictionless participation may be the key to increased citizen participation. A growing number of mayors is present at social media platforms, personally manages their accounts and participates in on-line discussions. New models of public participation are being implemented at local level – be it e-consultation platforms, gamification of the planning process, crowdfunding platforms and campaigns for community projects or participatory budgeting at municipal and neighborhood levels and schools or sectoral discussion on spending priorities.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Law no 85/2015 on Access to the Information

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